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CORRECT CONDUCT OF THE POPULATION IN EMERGENCY SITUATIONS

Jurayev Bobomurod Khudaynazarovich

Assistant

Karshi Engineering and Economic Institute

Department of Labor Protection and Technical Safety

Abstract: this article describes the behavior of the population in natural emergencies. This topic is relevant, since today, in the age of technological progress, various types of accidents, catastrophes with the death of people, material values, serious environmental violations, etc. occur in the world.

Key words: emergency situations, civil protection, natural disasters, natural, earthquakes, landslides, mudflows, floods, reservoirs, hydraulic structures, evacuation, snowfalls, medical service, personal hygiene, psychotraumatic

Natural emergencies can be caused by both natural and man-made sources. Natural sources have existed for thousands of years and do not have a significant impact on the imbalance in nature. The situation is somewhat different with artificial sources. Over the past 100-150 years, they have increasingly influenced the ecology of the earth and nature, and it is becoming more and more difficult in terms of its restoration. I mean deforestation, plowing of steppes, smoky air, release of oil on continents, in the seas and oceans, dumping of various wastes into the waters of rivers, seas and oceans. That is, artificial sources are caused by human activity. [1]

Let's focus on natural sources. For people inhabiting a particular area, they

are, as a rule, emergency situations of a catastrophic nature, since, firstly, they are practically unpredictable, and secondly, they are quite formidable phenomena that, arising in a populated area, lead to human casualties. to the victims.

Natural disasters are various natural phenomena that cause sudden disruptions to the normal functioning of the population, as well as destruction and destruction of material assets. They often have a negative impact on the environment.[2]

Natural disasters usually include geological (earthquakes, landslides, volcanic eruptions), hydrometeorological (floods, mudflows, snow drifts, droughts) and epidemiological (epidemic, epizootic, epiphytotic) phenomena.

Earthquakes are specific phenomena that occur in certain areas of the earth's crust. They can occur both on land and under water. Earthquakes have always amazed people with both their destructive power and consequences, expressed in the subsidence of the earth's crust, intensification of volcanic activity, the formation of tsunamis, etc.

It is very important for a person to know where and when an earthquake will occur. Modern science has information about where such a natural disaster of one force or another may occur, but it cannot yet predict the day and hour of it.

Work on earthquake forecasting has been going on for decades; in recent years, some progress has been made in this direction.

Precursors of earthquakes, as has already been established, can be indirect signs. In the period preceding an earthquake, for example, geodetic benchmarks are raised, and the parameters of the physical and chemical composition of groundwater change. These signs are recorded by special instruments at geophysical stations. The harbingers of possible earthquakes should also include some signs that the population of seismically dangerous areas should especially know; this is the appearance of the smell of gas in areas where the air was previously clean and a similar phenomenon had not previously been noted,

disturbance of birds and domestic animals shortly before tremors. All these signs can be grounds for warning the population about a possible earthquake.

Earthquakes have always caused varying degrees of mental disorder in people, manifested in abnormal behavior. An acute motor reaction is often followed by a depressive state with general motor retardation. As a result of this, as statistics show, most of the injuries received among the population are explained by the unconscious actions of the victims themselves, caused by a state of panic and fear.[3]

Is it possible to reduce the psycho-traumatic impact of an earthquake on a person?

Yes, perhaps, first of all, by instilling in each person a sense of high citizenship, courage, self-control, discipline, responsibility for the behavior of not only himself and his loved ones, but also the people around him at his place of residence, work or study.

If you are notified of the threat of an earthquake or signs of one appear, you must act quickly, but calmly, confidently and without panic.

When notified in advance of the threat of an earthquake, before leaving the apartment (house), it is necessary to turn off the heating devices and gas; if the stove was burning, extinguish it; then you need to dress the children, the elderly and dress yourself, take the necessary things, a small supply of food, medicine, documents and go outside. On the street, you should move away from buildings and structures as quickly as possible in the direction of squares, squares, wide streets, sports grounds, undeveloped areas, strictly observing the established public order. If the earthquake began unexpectedly, when it is not possible to get ready and leave the apartment (house), you need to take a place (stand) in the door or window opening; As soon as the first tremors of the earthquake subside, you should quickly go outside.

At enterprises and institutions during an earthquake, all work stops,

production and technological equipment stops. If, due to production conditions, it is impossible or impossible to stop a unit, furnace, production line, turbine, etc. in a short time, then they are transferred to a gentle operating mode.

If you are outside your apartment (house) or place of work during an earthquake, you should not rush home, you should calmly listen to the instructions of the relevant officials on actions in the current situation and act in accordance with such instructions. If you are on public transport, you cannot leave it while it is moving; you need to wait until the transport stops completely and get out of it calmly, letting children, disabled people, and the elderly pass first. Senior school students should help the management and teachers in maintaining order among junior schoolchildren.

After an earthquake or even in. During this process, work will be carried out to provide assistance to the victims and to eliminate the consequences of the earthquake. First of all, such work will be carried out by persons belonging to civil protection units. But the rest of the population, at the call of local authorities and civil protection authorities, must take part in priority rescue and emergency restoration work in areas of destruction.

Great assistance from the population can be provided to medical institutions and the civil protection medical service in maintaining normal sanitary and living conditions in places of temporary resettlement of the population affected by the earthquake. It is necessary to carefully observe the rules of personal hygiene and ensure that all family members follow them; you need to remind your neighbors and workmates about this.

Floods are severe natural disasters. The main causes of most floods are heavy rainfall, intense snow melting, river floods as a result of tidal waves or changes in wind at the mouth of the river.

Actions of the population during floods are carried out taking into account the flood warning time, as well as the experience of observing the manifestations

of this element in past years.

The suddenness of a flood causes the need for special behavior and actions of the population. If people live on the ground floor or other lower floors and there is rising water on the street, it is necessary to leave the apartments and go up to the upper floors; if the house is one-story, occupy the attic space. When at work, by order of the administration, you should, following the established procedure, take elevated places. While in the field, in case of sudden flooding, you should take elevated places or trees, use various kinds of floating objects (for example, inner tubes of agricultural equipment tires).[5]

The search for people in the flooded area is organized and carried out immediately, for this purpose the crews of floating means of civil protection units and all other available forces and means are involved.

Landslides occur as a result of a violation of the equilibrium conditions of slopes, most often along the banks of rivers and reservoirs; the main reason for their occurrence is the saturation of clayey rocks with groundwater to a plastic and fluid state, as a result of which huge masses of soil with all buildings and structures slide down the slope.

The behavior and actions of the population during mudflows and landslides is greatly influenced by the organization of timely detection and recording of signs of these natural disasters and the organization of notification (warning) about the disaster.

In most cases, the population can be warned about the danger of a mudflow in just tens of minutes and less often in 1–2 hours or more. The approach of such a flow can be heard by the characteristic sound of boulders and fragments of stones rolling and colliding with each other, reminiscent of the roar of a train approaching at high speed. [4]

The most effective way to combat mudflows is the advance implementation of a set of organizational, economic, agrotechnical, forest reclamation and

hydraulic measures.

The population in mudflow-prone areas is obliged to strictly follow the recommendations for cutting down forest plantations, farming, and grazing livestock. If there is a threat of a mudflow, dams are strengthened along the path of its movement to populated areas, embankments and temporary retaining walls are erected, mudflow traps, diversion ditches, etc. are installed. It is everyone's duty to participate in these works to the extent possible.

The initial sign of the onset of landslide movements is the appearance of cracks on buildings, breaks in roads, coastal fortifications and embankments, bulging of the earth, displacement of the base of various high-rise structures and even trees in the lower part relative to the upper.

Anti-landslide measures in which the population should take part are the drainage of surface water, tree planting, installation of various supporting engineering structures, excavation of trenches in order to drain the soil of the landslide massif, unloading and leveling of the landslide slope. In addition, the population living in landslide-prone areas should not allow excessive water leakage from taps, damaged water pipes or standpipes; It is necessary to temporarily arrange drainage drains when surface water accumulates (with the formation of puddles).

If the population is notified of an approaching mudflow or a landslide, as well as at the first signs of their manifestation, they must leave the premises as quickly as possible, warn others about the danger and go to a safe place. When leaving the premises, you should extinguish the stoves, turn off the gas valves and turn off the lights and electrical appliances. This will help prevent fires from occurring.

Snowfalls, which can last from 16 to 24 hours, have a strong impact on the economic activities of the population, especially in rural areas. The negative impact of this phenomenon is aggravated by blizzards (blizzards, snowstorms),

during which visibility sharply deteriorates and transport links, both intracity and intercity, are interrupted. Snow and rain at low temperatures and hurricane winds create conditions for icing of power lines, communications, electric transport contact networks, as well as the roofs of buildings, various types of supports and structures, which often causes their destruction.

In mountainous areas, after heavy snowfalls, the risk of avalanches will increase. The population will be notified of this by various warning signals installed in areas of possible avalanches and possible snow falls. These warnings should not be ignored; their recommendations must be strictly followed.[6]

To summarize the issues discussed in the article, natural disasters are a tragedy for the entire state, and especially for those areas of the country where they occur. As a result of natural disasters, the country's economy suffers, since production enterprises are destroyed, national wealth is destroyed and, most importantly, losses occur among people, their homes and property are destroyed.

Correct behavior of the population during natural disasters, based on knowledge of the basics of civil protection, is the basis for reducing human losses and material damage.[6]

Particularly important is the participation of the population in the work to eliminate the consequences of natural disasters, as a prerequisite for the speedy restoration of normal life of the population in the area affected by the natural disaster.

It should be noted that actions of the population during natural disasters and during the liquidation of their consequences must be carried out in strict accordance with the instructions of civil protection authorities

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